

FLAGSHIP
UNIVERSITY
OF OULU

10.5281/zenodo.14188870

6G FLAGSHIP

Towards a Sustainable 6G: Research Activities at the 6G Flagship

Marcos Katz

Centre for Wireless Communications

University of Oulu, Finland

WWRF49 Poznan, Poland

- **Introduction to 6G Flagship**

- **Towards Truly Sustainable Communication Systems**
 - Communication Systems for Sustainability
 - Sustainable Communication Systems
 - Example

At the heart of Oulu University's research profile

- **6G Flagship program 2018-2026.**
- 6G Flagship budget total will be 292,2M€
- The Academy of Finland and the University of Oulu are the biggest financers.
- University of Oulu's funding 123,3M€ during 2018-2028.

**LEARN MORE ABOUT
OUR RESEARCH**

Strategic profiling themes at the University of Oulu.

6G Playground

The first-ever 6G white paper came out in 2019. Since then, other white papers have envisioned various future scenarios.

The 6G research visions will take you on a journey to explore the possibilities and imagine the opportunities in the 2030s.

READ MORE ON
OUR VISIONS

6G Flagship Strategic Research Areas

6G Flagship research is organized into four strategic research areas (SRA)

**WIRELESS
CONNECTIVITY**

Enabling Unmanned
Processes

**DEVICES AND CIRCUIT
TECHNOLOGY**

Enabling Unlimited
Connectivity

**DISTRIBUTED
INTELLIGENCE**

Enabling Time Critical &
Trusted Apps

**HUMAN-CENTRIC
WIRELESS SERVICES**

Enabling Disruptive Value
Networks

KPIs 2018 – 2022

Science

- 1,891** Peer-reviewed Publications
 - 24,7% Publications in Top 10% citation percentile
 - 2,29 Field-weighted Citation Impact (FWCI)
 - 1244 (65,8%) Joint international publications
 - 1,803 Open access / self-archived publications
- 73** Doctoral degrees
 - 265,416 Doctoral thesis downloads
- 3** ERC Advanced Grants
- 2** Academy of Finland Professors

Co-creation and business impact

- 337** Research projects, external funding
- 428** Company collaborators
- 140** Companies funding projects
- 221** Joint publications with companies
- 7,575** participants in co-creation forums
- 994,579** 6G White Paper downloads
- 170,000** Vision video downloads

Societal impact

- 8,501** Social media followers
 - 1,189,185 Tweet views
- 5,738** Articles in independent media
- 309,995** 6G Waves downloads

Staff

- 446** Staff (20% female)
- 48** Nationalities (44% Finns)
- 32** Professors and tenures

6G Visions and Research Directions

► 6gflagship.com/white-papers

6G

Read further – Take a look at the 6G White Papers

White papers available at
6gflagship.com/white-papers

6G

6G FLAGSHIP

Towards Truly Sustainable Wireless Communication Systems

- **Sustainability** is a complex and multi-dimensional concept
- **6G Flagship** is actively developing sustainable wireless communication solutions
- What do we mean by **sustainable communications** or in general **sustainability** when referring to communication systems?
- Defining sustainability and sustainable wireless communications is important!

Sustainability and sustainable development

Sustainability¹ refers to the “principle of ensuring that our actions today do not limit the range of economic, social, and environmental options open to future generations”.

Sustainable development² refers to the “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”.

¹J. Elkington. Cannibals with forks: The triple bottom line of 21st-century business. Capstone Publishing Ltd. 1997.

²World Commission on Environment and Development’s Brundtland report ‘Our Common Future’. 1987.

Sustainable Wireless Communications

**Wireless
Communication
Systems**

Wireless communication
system for sustainability

Sustainable wireless
communication system

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

**Part of the
solution!**

**Part of the
problem!**

Example: 80% of a smartphone's environmental impact is produced before a device reaches the consumer.

In Brief: The Sustainability Landscape at CWC/6G Flagship

- UN SDG, ITU contributions, white papers, regulation, business, visions, etc.
- **6GESS** Programme: 6G Enabled Sustainable Society
 - Healthcare & Energy Systems
- Connectivity to remote/undeveloped areas: research, white paper, etc.

- Sustainable communication systems: research focused mostly on energy issues (energy efficiency, low energy solutions, energy harvesting, etc.)
- Truly Sustainable Communication Systems Work Force

- We identify megatrends influencing sustainable development of 6G.
- We develop a novel linkage between 6G and the UN SDGs
- Three-fold role of 6G as a 1) a provider of services to help support activities towards reaching the UN SDGs, 2) a measuring tool for reporting of indicators; and 3) a reinforcer of developing 6G in line with the UN SDG.

- **Energy efficiency, low-power solutions, energy harvesting, spectral efficiency**, etc. are important aspects of sustainable communications
 - Whenever we focus on these aspects, we can well say that we are working on sustainable communications
 - We also did so in the past, and we referred to this as **green communications**
 - **How do we approach sustainability today?** Can we do it in a wider, **holistic sense**?

A holistic approach to sustainable communication systems

6G FLAGSHIP

**Towards Truly Sustainable Wireless Communication
Systems:**

Shall we start with IoT systems?

- **Forecast:** by next decade, 100s of billions IoT devices will be deployed across the globe.
- IoT is often referred as one of the key technologies to
 - fight against climate change
 - support the efficient use of (Earth) resources

But, is IoT technology itself sustainable?

- Technology could be defeating its purpose

- Developing IoT systems is in general less demanding than other wireless communication systems.
 - Less demanding requirements/performance.
 - Reduced implementation complexity.
- IoT offers a unique opportunity to further extend the concept of sustainable communications.

The cost and impact of connecting billions of IoT must be considered.

Resources have to be used in a sustainable manner.

Sustainable IoT:

- **Converged infrastructure** able to provide multiple services.
- **Energy-autonomous** IoT nodes
- **Sustainable node implementation**
- **Efficient use of resources** (energy, spectrum, physical resources)
- **Minimum environmental impact**

**SUPERIOT: TRULY SUSTAINABLE PRINTED
ELECTRONICS-BASED IOT COMBINING OPTICAL
AND RADIO WIRELESS TECHNOLOGIES**

Project Overview

- **Project Name:** SUPERIOT
 - **Project website:** superiot.eu
- **Stream:** STREAM-B-01-03
- **Members:** University of Oulu (FI), INESC TEC (PT), VTT (FI), NOVA (PT), IMEC (NL), LIGHTBEE (ES), MPICOSYS (PL), KU Leuven (BE), University of Bristol (UK), VIVID Components (DE), WAVECOM (PT).
- **Other: Budget:** €5M; **duration:** 3 years; **demonstrators:** 4
- **Keywords:** truly sustainable IoT, printed electronics, optical communications, radio communications.
- **Verticals:** logistics, industry, healthcare, consumer market, wearables.

Uniqueness of SUPERIOT

- **SUPERIOT** offers a unique holistic approach to sustainable IoT
 - Sustainable by design
 - Sustainable by implementation
 - **Use of printed electronics technology**
 - Sustainable by usage
- **SUPERIOT** combines **light and radio technologies**
 - to provide wireless connectivity
 - to support energy autonomous operation of nodes/devices
 - to provide reliable and accurate positioning
 - **Reconfigurability**: to create a highly flexible and adaptable IoT system
- **SUPERIOT** will develop proof-of-concept demonstrators to validate the created.

SUPERIOT will develop a future-proof concept, paving the way towards novel technologies. In the next decade, we might see:

- **Fully-printed advanced capabilities reconfigurable optical-radio IoT nodes**
- **Extremely inexpensive nodes** (e.g., one-cent node)
- **Environmentally friendly disposable IoT nodes**, use of biodegradable electronics, etc.
- **Novel scenarios/use cases**: inside the human body, underwater, mining, etc.

- **Wireless communication system: a) for sustainability, and b) being sustainable.**
- **Developing a truly sustainable communication system**
 - Holistic approach
- **Sustainability metrics needs to be developed**
 - How to clearly and unambiguously measure sustainability
 - Fair comparison between solutions
 - Sustainability regulations
- Will future (6G) communications standards define figures directly or indirectly related to sustainability?

Thank you!

FLAGSHIP
UNIVERSITY
OF OULU

6GFLAGSHIP.COM • #6GFLAGSHIP

